

RISK PREDICTION OF BREAST CANCER FROM REAL TIME STREAMING HEALTH DATA USING MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

With the expansion of data in healthcare exact analysis of medical data helps in detecting disease early. Breast cancer is among the cancers that cause high amount of fatalities each year in many women around globe and this is the most popular form of all tumors that is lead cause of women's deaths. Conventional data mining approaches and classification techniques are broadly used particularly when dealing medical or health data but the new challenges includes applying machine learning on huge and continuous streaming data. In order to carry out this challenge a big data analysis platform which uses in-memory clustering known as Apache Spark can be effectively utilized to monitor data events against machine learning. In this work machine learning models are built using five different algorithms with breast cancer data as option of using. The performance is analyzed and the one with highest performance is used to build final model which is used against streaming data to predict the risk of disease in real time. So, this paper aims at developing complete prediction system to which data attributes are ingested from some source and it predicts the risk of disease for the required ingested data streams in real time. The dataset used in this study is "Wisconsin Breast Cancer Data-Set (WBCD)" imported from UCI repository and it needs some preprocessing in order to prepare it for machine learning. The five classifiers used to build offline model are Logistic Regression, Random forest, Gradient boosted trees, Decision tree, and Support vector machine out of these five classifiers best in terms of accuracy specificity and sensitivity i.e. Random forest in our case, is selected in order to predict risk of disease in real-time.

Keywords: Big data streaming; Breast Cancer; Dataframes; MLlib; Netcat Server; Spark;

Abbreviations: DT, Decision Tree; MLlib, machine learning library; LR, Logistic Regression; SVM, Support Vector machine; RF, Random Forest; ML, machine learning; GBT, Gradient Boosted trees.

I. INTRODUCTION

Generally, the most leading cause of death in women's is lung cancer while second most common causes is breast cancer[1]. The most common practice for diagnosing and detecting breast cancer is either examining physically or analyzing images[2]. We have seen significant changes in amounts of data collected and created and we are in a position to evaluate, process and mine huge chunks of data. So, predicting and detecting the phases of cancer early can lead to less deaths and early decision can really save many people's lives. Big data science, machine learning are two key fields which several researchers have identified as main research subject especially in medical field[2][3].

Digital information has become even more useful in many fields such as health care. Predicting rapidly occurring streaming data events is the main challenging when dealing with machine learning, that is where apache spark comes into the picture. Spark being analytics platform for big data have machine learning capabilities as well as many other features. Current spark framework comprises of streaming, Sql, GraphX and MLlib. MLlib is a machine learning library which supports all classification and clustering algorithms. This paper mainly focuses on building prediction system which uses sparks streaming, Sql and MLlib. Different classifiers are used and analyzed with the use case breast cancer data and final streaming application is built using best performer classifier. The classifiers used for building offline model are LR, RF, SVM, GBT and DT. The concept of RDD (Resilient Distributed Dataset) that spark provides brace such applications. RDD's could be loaded into memory without divisions among queries. They rebuild missing data if failure occurs. RDD's know how they were constructed from data (by function like join group-by or map). This is the main reason of sparks efficiency as it speeds up process hundred times[4][5].

Furthermore, paper is organized as section two describes related works in this field. Section three defines the presentation of proposed research, dataset and methodology. Section Four describes results and discussions related to this research and finally paper ends in section five with conclusion.

II. RELATED WORK

Much work on data analysis is a hot topic for a large number of scientists, mainly in the medical field. Sparks MLlib is commonly used in practice to predict health and risk status.

In [2] the principal focus is on building prediction system with the help of Sparks MLlib and streaming data. This can be considered as distributed machine learning collecting appropriate provided data events continuously and then predicting the status regarding health. The use of decision tree in particular improved the efficiency and efficacy of built health prediction system. The disease dataset which is considered for the research is breast cancer.

In [6] The motive of this research is also to prepare prediction system which can predict heart disease when data in real time is fed to the system. RF is being used for building offline model with sparks MLlib. The framework comprises of two primary subparts which includes processing and visualization. TCP messages are sent to system where the disease is predicted in instantaneously.

In [5] Modular heart disease identification framework is created using sparks MLlib and streaming which is also put on cloud for testing purpose. Twitter is used to send attributes as tweet containing heart disease related data from six different user accounts which are then transferred to created system to identify the disease.

In [7] A neural based algorithm is proposed for prediction using machine learning on huge data from health-care communities. Compared to many algorithms common for predictions, proposed algorithm hits its predictive accuracy 94.8 percent at a higher convergence pace than CNN.

In [8] Two data mining algorithms are utilized to predict cancer survivability the data used is lung cancer and techniques followed are SVM and LR. Paper concludes that most studies work on classification rather than data filtering and cleaning which is more suitable and appropriate for data mining.

In [9] Big data analyses were performed using Sparks MLlib and HDFS with java and Scala. Moreover, the word big data is a phenomenon of the decade nowadays with the technological revolution, it has a huge effect on our developments in sciences. Exploring big data tool well is currently a required demand. Hadoop is basic Big Data Analysis technology but acts to be slow because the job results must be processed for each process before the next phase begins and the delays of replication.

III. DESCRIPTION OF PROPOSED WORK

Main aim of this study is to present a complete prediction framework which predicts breast cancer risk in real time. The foremost objectives of this work can be fulfilled when taking the desired steps in sequence to build the needed system. The architecture of the proposed prediction framework is shown in figure 1.

A. Methodology

In order to carry out this work successfully different phases are followed in sequence which are defined in the fig 1. In the systemic studying breast cancer disease prescient review is done using Apache Spark's MLlib. Five classification techniques are used to build models and parameters including accuracy, specificity and sensitivity are estimated. The algorithms utilized to investigate the performance are LR, RF, GBT, SVM, DT. Out of these five one with highest accuracy is selected to include in streaming model. The primary focus remains on streaming data when model is created for final streaming application the whole data set of breast cancer is used to train model and test data is the streaming data which is ingested from socket streams.

Figure 1. Architecture of prediction system in Spark

B. Dataset

The proposed work uses "breast-cancer-wisconsin.csv" data-set imported from UCI repository of machine learning. This data-set consists of 699 records and 11 attributes. full information and description of used dataset in in table 1. The field "class" in the dataset represents whether the cancer is benign (not harmful in effect) or malignant (very virulent or infectious) where integer value 2 represents benign and 4 as malignant. The attribute class in our case is normalized and value 2 is replaced by 0 and 4 is replaced by 1. Also, the attribute "Bare Nuclei" contains missing values which are filled by the mean values of this column in our study. when working for building machine learning model attribute "id" is dropped as it is of no use in prediction. Most of the studies have used this breast cancer database while trying to compute the performance of classifiers but in our case, we have not just compared various classifiers but prepared a framework to which continuous data is fed for prediction in real time. This data set is selected throughout the research as it arrives from a reputable source and is publicly available. It was also used in a variety of past machine learning studies.

Table1 Attribute names of breast cancer dataset

Sno	Attributes	Description
1	Id no.	Sample code number
2	Clump Thickness	1 - 10
3	Uniformity of Cell Size:	1 - 10
4	Uniformity of Cell Shape:	1 - 10
5	Marginal Adhesion:	1 - 10
6	Single Epithelial Cell Size:	1 - 10
7	Bare Nuclei:	1 - 10
8	Bland Chromatin:	1 - 10
9	Normal Nucleoli:	1 - 10
10	Mitoses:	1 - 10
11	Class: (2 for benign, 4 for malignant)	Changed to 0 for benign and 1 for malignant

C. Machine learning Models

Spark's python API also known as pyspark is a platform intended to manage and analyze big data also having ML and streaming capabilities. Developing a breast cancer risk detection framework, we have to go through different phases. Firstly, getting data from open source online repository of ML then preprocess it which includes dropping unnecessary attributes and filling absent values of other attribute columns. Secondly when data is prepared for machine learning model, we have variety of choices for selecting classification technique. MLlib of spark espouses all algorithms of classification as well as clustering that can accommodate huge databases.

As for as building offline models is concerned five algorithms are utilized and their comparison is done on the basis of performance when models are created while data set is broken as 70% for training and 30% for testing. The five algorithms of classification used are LR, GBT, SVM, RF and DT. The performance values such as accuracy specificity and sensitivity for each of algorithms are computed and analyzed. The best thing about using python within spark is that we can use other python libraries within our work so many python libraries are utilized to get the confusion matrices of all five classifiers as well as display the performance values. Confusion matrices are helpful by evaluating them we can get values of accuracy specificity and sensitivity manually using equations below.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

When using five classifiers for offline model each of the classifier is also tested for continuously changing values of their respective parameter values like for DT max Depth and maxBins values are changed to rectify on what value a particular classifier performs better. Similarly, for all five algorithms different parameter values are used. The parameters used for each of the algorithms will be discussed in next section. The flowchart of the work is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 flow chart of the work to build prediction system

The meaning of the values obtained in the confusion matrix are shown in figure 3.

	Predicted No 0	Predicted Yes 1
Actual No	TN	FP
Actual Yes	FN	TP
TP (True Positive): We predicted yes (they have the disease) in these and the disease is real.		
TN (True Negatives): We predicted no, and they do not have any illness.		
FP (False positives): Yes expected, but actually they don't have the disease.		
FN (False Negatives): We predicted no, but the disease does exist.		

Figure 3 Matrix values definition

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At first data-set for breast cancer was being analyzed and preprocessing steps were performed including dropping unnecessary attribute columns and filling missing values for some attributes. Five models were built with certain parameters using five algorithms. While building models confusion matrix values we get for each algorithm are shown in table 2 below.

Table 2 confusion matrices of five classifiers

RF		GBT		LR		DT		SVM	
129	2	126	5	129	2	127	4	130	1
0	69	2	67	1	68	5	64	13	56

The resultant accuracy specificity and sensitivity when using different parameters for each algorithm are shown in table 3 below as it can be seen from table highest performance is shown by the RF classifier. Thus, RF is selected as technique used for building final machine learning pipeline which predicts status of disease when continuous streams of data are fed to it. Comparison of these algorithms based on the performance parameters obtained is shown in figure 3.

Table 3 confusion matrices of five classifiers

Algorithm	Specificity	Sensitivity	Accuracy
RF maxDepth = 2; maxBins =32; numTrees =20	98.47	100	99
GBT	96.18	97.10	96.5
LR maxIter =10	98.47	98.5	98.5
DT maxDepth =3 MaxBins=10	95.5	90	95.5
SVM maxIter = 5; regParam =0.01;	99.23	81	93

Thus, RF being best performer as a result, for the final streaming data prediction system RF is used in the pipeline in order to detect cancer to be benign or malignant. The input stream sent for defect prediction is rendered by using a TCP message through a Net-cat server. In the proposed work patient attributes are fed through Netcat server using TCP socket connection through specific port number and data is received by spark streaming context. The text sent must be in predefined format and data of one individual should start using specific keyword (TWEET_APP in our case). These data attributes are passed through stages. firstly, the data stream gets split into tokens, tokens into filtered words by removing stop words and finally words are converted into vectors and the final pipeline is build using these three stages and selected classification algorithm i.e. RF.

Figure 3 Comparison graph of algorithms

In context of streaming framework creation, the whole data-set is used for training and the stream data acts as test data which gives prediction values in real time. The output is generated on the net cat server where from data attributes are actually fed. The output comes in the form of table where for each individual data attribute there is corresponding predicted value.

This prediction system provides a structure for data processing in real time analyzing health info. The fundamental goal of this is not performing basic data analytics but apply machine learning on streaming data using big data approach. Details of several of the transmitted data streams in predetermined order can be seen in table 4.

Table 4 Result of fed data streams to predict risk of breast cancer

Live Text Stream (Clump_Thickness, Uniformity_of_Cell_Size, UniformityofCellShape, MarginalAdhesion, SingleEpithelialCellSize, BareNuclei, BlandChromatin, NormalNucleoli,	Predicted value
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Mitoses, Class)	
TWEET_APP 6 4 4 3 5 2 3 2 2	1
TWEET_APP 6 8 1 3 2 1 3 1 2	1
TWEET_APP 4 1 1 3 2 1 3 1 1	0
TWEET_APP 3 1 1 3 2 1 3 1 1	0
TWEET_APP 6 7 10 8 7 8 9 7 1	1
TWEET_APP 8 10 10 10 8 9 7 1 1	1

So, data streams of different individuals in a sequence are passed to spark streaming which further splits and processes it in order to prepare it for ML pipeline. In this work streams are passed using Net-cat server but with modification different tools like Kafka and twitter can be used to ingest data and perform prediction on enormous data fed continuously. Our study is not restricted to basic data analysis but a framework is developed to predict disease in real time that is more about distributed ML. Having availability of more feasible health related datasets other diseases can be predicted as well. With the use case dataset, we acquired highest accuracy of 99%. While comparing our ML model with (Ed-daoudy 2019)[2] we got 4% more accuracy as they obtained 95.5% using decision tree. on Comparison with [1]we got 2% more accuracy as they have acquired 97% accuracy when using SVM. Overall, as per our knowledge our model's performance is better than existing researches in terms of specificity, accuracy and sensitivity and among the existing researches very few have worked on streaming data.

V. CONCLUSION

while concluding we can say a full prediction framework is built around the spark using machine learning, spark streaming, SQL spark and data frames. The models are built to test which classifier proves to be better in terms of performance and we concluded that RF proves to be better among all with respect to the use case data set. We know that with time health related data is increasing rapidly from numerous sources so instantaneous framework is needed which can predict while continuous attributes are transmitted to it. Breast cancer is the second leading disease that affects most women in the world after lung cancer, attributes in the individual can be examined either by imaging or by physically so knowing the attribute values, arranging them as per data set used for training our system can predict whether patient has breast cancer as malignant or benign. This is going to save a lot of time and effort as conventional technologies are not in well potential to handle streaming data and perform distributed machine learning at the same time.

Future Scope

The main focus of the risk management program is always on prompt response to save individuals from greater losses. There are many diseases for which one might think about developing a system to predict a specific disease early. With AI and ML, the complete system needs to be developed on the basis of high accuracy which is not misleading.

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